

Public Participation through Procurement Planning for Sustainable Procurement in Devolved System of Governments in Kenya

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Abstract

Public participation is a concept enshrined in the Kenyan constitution, 2010 with intention to devolve powers to the common citizens and increase transparency and accountability hence play a role towards public procurement sustainability. Sustainable procurement seeks to ensure public procurement is done in a responsible way taking account of maximum utilization of resources to attain value for money across the whole procurement process. By involving citizens in the procurement planning process in devolved systems of government seeks to allow them to chooses projects of their choice and participate in supplying local available materials and services making the projects sustainable from the social responsibility perspective. Studies on the role of citizens in the procurement planning in county government in kenya is scanty. Therefore the study sought to evaluate how public participation is achieved through procurement planning and its influence on sustainable procurement in devolved systems of government in Kenya. The study adopted descriptive study design. With a target population of 1146. A sample of 297 respondents was chosen through stratified sampling method from Makueni, Machakos, and Kitui Counties. Primary data was collected by use of semi structured questionnaires, descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse data. SPSS aided in data analysis. The findings of the study show a positive and linear relationship between procurement planning and sustainable procurement ($r=0.659$, $p<0.05$). The regression model was a good fit as indicated by a significant F-statistic ($F=220.516$, $p<0.05$). The study therefore recommends that County governments need to adopt effective procurement planning techniques so as to reap the benefits of public participation in procurement process for sustainable procurement management. The study proposes that other counties be investigated in order to have a holistic picture of the entire country on the subject matter.

Keywords: Devolution, Public participation, procurement planning, sustainable procurement, sustainability, Green Procurement, Strategy

1.0 Introduction

Sustainable procurement is a mechanism by which organizations fulfill their needs for products, facilities, works, and utilities in a way that provides long-term value for capital, providing benefits not only to the organization, but also to society and the economy, thus minimizing environmental harm (Australasian Procurement and Construction Council (APCC), 2013). World Bank (2019) further describes Sustainable procurement as a process which incorporates sustainability considerations throughout the procurement process in order to achieve optimal value for money in delivering development objectives. Sustainable procurement management (SPM) is therefore an approach to achieve sustainability because it also takes environmental factor in consideration, in decisions of supply chain management (Tiwari, Wei & Nor., (2019); Yook et al., 2017; Zailani et al., 2012). Sustainability has now become a dominant topic of discussion among purchasing and supply professionals, along with traditional metrics such as cost, quality, and delivery time. According to Council of Institute of Procurement and Supply ((CIPS), 2009) sustainability is on the mainstream agenda for both private and public sector organizations. Oracle (2015) states that; the spotlight of the procurement function today has shifted from minimizing costs to maximizing value. However, even though sustainability issues are top of the global academic and non-academic debate, there is still limited literature and understanding of the concept of sustainable procurement (Seuring et al, 2010). Sustainable procurement goes by many different

names: green procurement, environmental procurement, affirmative procurement, responsible procurement, socially responsible procurement etc (CIPS, 2012).

External pressures are often crucial in kickstarting the engagement of organisations in sustainable procurement; however, for it to become truly successful, certain organisational factors are needed (Hoejmose & Adrien-Kirby, 2012). It is inside the organisation that changes have to be made and barriers removed to achieve the desired outcomes in society. The sustainable procurement literature has given much attention to the identification of barriers to sustainable procurement (Ageron, Gunasekaran, & Spalanzani, 2011; Giunipero, Hooker, & Denslow, 2012; Günther & Scheibe, 2006; Meehan & Bryde, 2011; Michelsen & de Boer, 2009; Preuss, 2009; Varnas, Balfors, & Faith-Ell, 2009; Walker & Brammer, 2009). According to various literature, these barriers are part of societal challenges: planning, monitoring and contract management. Although the literature on sustainable procurement clearly identifies these factors as being influential (Meehan & Bryde, 2011; Preuss, 2009; Walker & Brammer, 2009), no attention has been given to how the community actually influence the degree of sustainable procurement. This study concentrated on procurement planning as a public participation approach and its effect on sustainable procurement.

According to COK (2010) public participation has been poised to help in priority setting and providing feedback on government funded projects. UNDP (2016) states that Sustainable development tries to establish synergies between environmental balance, social progress and economic feasibility under the principle of good governance. The meaningful and effective engagement of citizens and other actors, including stakeholders in public decision-making processes is one of the key issues facing public organizations, (Beach, 2008). According to Centre for Governance and Development and National taxpayers association ((CGDNTA), 2009) one of the characteristics of good procurement is participatory which implies that the suppliers, citizens and other stakeholders effectively contribute to the operations of public procurement and in the preparation of the essential legislation as and when necessary. In other words, the allocation and use of sizeable public funds is decided by public procurement, and with it, many of the key decisions associated with public policies and services in the region materialize, becoming in themselves a privileged tool for promoting social, economic and environmental policies (Inter-American Development Bank, 2016).

Public participation in Ghana seeks to enhance accountability, transparency and oversight capacities of duty-bearers at the local government level, to promote increased public confidence, participation in elections and to promote the increased participation of women and youth in decision making processes. According to Afrobarometer (2014), as active members of the democratization process, Ghanaians have the responsibility of holding their leaders to account as well as helping to improve the mechanisms by which citizens hold their leaders accountable. He further asserts that increased transparency in the use of public resources and other government initiatives involves ensuring that citizens have easy access to information, which also showed a positive impact on the demand for accountability. Public procurement utilizes public resources hence becomes one of the key areas where accountability is highly required. It is evidenced that as national literacy rate improves, Ghana citizens become more aware of their rights and are able to ask public officials to account for their stewardship (Afrobarometer, 2014).

Similar to Kenya's public procurement systems, Ghana's public procurement is regulated by an Act of Parliament which was passed into law in December 2003, Act 633. Section 59 of Ghana's Public Procurement Act, 2003 (Act 663) includes some economic and social sustainable issues (Adjei, 2013). In Ghana, government procurement constitutes over 50% of the government budget. It's therefore presumed the government may make a difference and contribute to sustainable development if it buys goods and services that have been designed, produced and supplied having factored in the environment and social risks (Government of Ghana, 2013). Mathew (2012) revealed that if implemented effectively, sustainable procurement has the

potential to cut costs, shorten timescales, enhance stakeholder relationships, increase sales, reduce risks, enhance reputation and improve margins. In general most of the countries apart from the EU integrate reservations for marginalized groups and other aspects of public procurement that incorporate social aspects beyond labor laws, such as human rights, into regulation and practices, as is the case in many SSA countries such as South Africa, Kenya, Zimbabwe, Namibia, Uganda, and Botswana, as well as in the USA and Canada (Cravero, 2017).

Kenyan promulgated a new Constitution in August 2010 which ushered in a new system of governance with two levels of government; Central Government and 47 County Governments, which are distinct and interdependent (GoK, 2010). The creation of County Governments was meant to devolve governance to the grass root level which has been under implementation since the general elections on March 2013. Devolution in Kenya is meant to foster public participation in management of public affairs; a system that seeks to facilitate greater citizen involvement and control in public affairs including planning, budgeting and resource allocation among others (CoK, 2010). Devolution is founded on grounds of ensuring strong civilian oversight and engagement that calls for the involvement of citizens in key County Government processes (CoK, 2010). Beyond being a constitutional requirement, public participation and civilian oversight remains one of the most powerful tools in demanding for increasing transparency, accountability and efficiency in public procurement (Muriungi, 2014). The Kenyan government has put in place a wide range of policy, institutional and legislative policies to govern all business activities in a move towards sustainability in procurement processes. These include; Environmental Management and Coordination Act (EMCA) 2015 (Republic of Kenya, 2015), Kenya Solid Waste Management by laws of 2014 (Republic of Kenya, 2014), the Environmental Management and Coordination Regulations, (Republic of Kenya, 2014) and ISO (14001) environmental standards certification. According to GoK (2015) guidelines are given to various institution mostly public institutions to enhance accountability by involving different stakeholders at different levels of any procurement proceedings. The Public Procurement and Regulatory Authority (PPRA) (GoK, 2015) has a green procurement clause, which entails practices that encourage organizations to safeguard the environment. The public procurement regulations, 2020 has a community participation as one of the methods public entities can use when procuring for their requirement. This and many more regulations and laws to a great extent is an indication that public participation may be a game change to attaining sustainable procurement.

The County Government's Policy frameworks for public participation are based on the principles of inclusivity, accountability, diversity, building community participation, transparency, flexibility, accessibility, trust, commitment, respect and integration (GoK, 2012). The County Government Act 2012, article 91 acknowledges that particular structures for participation should be set up by the County Governments that allow public invitation to engage in county hall meetings, notice boards, vacancy announcement, job appointments, tenders and procurement awards, development sites and establishment of citizen's forum at county and decentralized units (CRECO, 2014). In Makueni County public participation mechanisms and institutional framework was established soon after the County government was established. According to Makueni County Government public participation framework (2013) the county seeks to utilize the various levels of participation promoting consultation, placation and partnership and citizens models of participation. The framework further clarifies that the government will adopt forms of public participation such as informing by providing information to help them understand the issues, options and solutions, consulting with the public to obtain their feedback on alternatives or decisions, involving the public to ensure their concerns are considered throughout the decision making process especially in development of decisions criteria and options, collaborating with the public to develop decision criteria and alternatives and identify the preferred solutions and empowering the public by placing final decision making authority in their hands.

The Public Participation framework states clearly that public participation is not meant to convey decisions already made but to generate and confirm decisions. Borrowing from the County Government Act (2012), the Makeni, Kitui and Machakos County Government Public Participation frameworks (2013), state that Public Participation is not a political process but a non-partisan process that involves the agent going to take instruction and direction from the public. Under this PP frameworks, stakeholders participate in community based infrastructure projects through involvement in procurement planning, monitoring and evaluating project performance, risk management and policy making process. Makeni county government was ranked number one County in public participation in Kenya (World bank, 2016). Well established public participation structures ensure timely and accurate sharing of information across the county for the enhancement of transparency and accountability (Oduor, Wanjiru, & Kisamwa, 2015). A county shall deliver services while observing the principles of equity, efficiency, accessibility, nondiscrimination, transparency, and accountability, sharing of data and information, and subsidiarity (Lubale, 2012).

Sustainable Public procurement is a significant activity in the developing world with a study of 106 developing countries finding that the purchases of their governments account for approximately 5.1 percent of their combined national outputs (Evenett & Hoekman, 2005) and Kenya is not an exception. If implemented effectively, sustainable procurement has the potential to cut costs, shorten timescales, enhance stakeholder relationships, increase sales, reduce risks, enhance reputation and improve margins (Mathew, 2017). The World Bank estimates that twenty five percent of Africa's GDP is lost to corruption every year. The Kenya government loses about one-third of the national budget annually to corruption with 80 percent of all corruption cases before the Ethics and Anti-Corruption Commission (EACC) have a procurement element (TIK, 2014). This is further emphasized by the (World Bank & IFC, 2007) indicating that in order to secure a government contract, a gift whose value represents 8 to 10 percent of the contract amount was expected. Similarly, according to the Institute for Development Studies ((IDS, 2012) manufacturing firms in Kenya spend an average of 14 percent of the value of government contracts on kickbacks. Public Procurement Oversight Authority (PPOA), 2007) estimated that procuring entities were buying goods and services at an average of 60 percent above the prevailing market price. Given the large amounts of money involved in government procurement, it is in the citizens' interests that the procurement process promotes prudent use of resources, integrity and fairness, ensuring value for money in the acquisition of goods and services.

Evidence on the performance of community participation approach is scant, but the work that is available suggests that practitioners may be overoptimistic and naive about the benefits of the approach (Mansuri & Rao, 2004). In fact, Mansuri and Rao (2004) conclude that little is known about the effects of community participation on sustainable procurement management in community-based projects. In view of the above facts, it is clear that public participation may have far reaching benefits in ensuring transparency and accountability in procurement process and that most County Governments have not fully enjoyed the benefits that public participation brings with it, therefore the study intended to establish the influence of public participation in procurement process for sustainable procurement management in devolved systems of Government in Kenya to fill this gap.

2.0 Literature Review

Procurement planning is a process whereby professionals establish what needs to be procured (goods, services or works), when they need to be procured (contract timeframes) and from what source (identifying suitable contractors and vendors). A procurement plan helps Procurement entities to achieve maximum value for expenditures and enables the entities to identify and address all relevant issues pertaining to a particular procurement before they can publicize their procurement notices to potential suppliers of goods, works and services (GoK, 2015). According to State Supply Commission (2016) procurement planning involves

consulting key stakeholders to define requirements, analyzing how the supply market works, assessing risks and ultimately defining the best procurement strategy to meet the agency's business needs. For effective and sustainable development to be realized, the community, which is the major beneficiary of the project, must participate through project implementation committees in, project planning and other aspects such as budgeting, resource identification, procurement and allocation of resources (Mulwa, 2008). AfriCOG (2015) states that according to the Auditor-General's 2014-2015 financial year report, most Counties have had adhoc, unplanned spending. It further asserts that the unplanned spending may indicate the total lack of procurement plans, or the ineffective use of existing procurement plans in anticipating all the activities to be undertaken. The success of a project will be enhanced if people with relevant knowledge and skills are involved at the beginning and throughout all processes (RDTL, 2011). Sustainability considerations should be incorporated into significant procurement plans. The plan should document each element of the procurement planning process, including the demand and supply market analyses and the likely impact on the supply market (The State of Queensland, 2014).

According to the constitution of Kenya 2010 planning for development priorities needs to be devolved to lower levels (wards and villages) to ensure representation. However, the expectations of planners and the public must be roughly equivalent for the process to be effective (Bob, 2003). Benefits of citizen participation to the planning process include; information and ideas on public issues, public support for planning decisions, avoidance of protracted conflicts and costly delays, reservoir of good will which can carry over to future decisions; and Spirit of cooperation and trust between the agency and the public (Bob, 2003; Cogan & Sharp, 1986). Involving stakeholders with direct interest in the strategic planning process provides broad support to the strategic plan and serves as a guarantee for its successful implementation, as the ownership over the produced strategic plan is adopted by all the community members involved in the planning process (Cosma et al., 2015). Governments are increasingly becoming aware that public participation is not only beneficial to the public, but can go a long way in ensuring that the governments are seen as responsive to the public needs and improves the quality of public services (Mchunu, 2012). Sustainable procurement is about taking social and environmental factors into consideration alongside financial factors in making procurement decisions. It involves looking beyond the traditional economic parameters and making decisions based on the whole life cost, the associated risks, measures of success and implications for society and the environment. Making decisions in this way requires setting procurement into the broader strategic context including value for money, performance management, corporate and community priorities (CIPS, 2014).

It is understood that the incorporation of citizen participation in public procurement allows for the generation of broader processes of government openness in decision-making as to how public spending is used and allocated, as well as fostering processes of citizen monitoring, social oversight of government management and vertical public accountability (Zuleta, 2019) that would otherwise be extremely complicated to implement successfully. From its perspective, public procurement is a key pillar of strategic governance and service -managed public procurement can and should play a major role in recommendation document is based on twelve principles. The philosophy of priority-driven budgeting is that resources should be allocated according to how effectively a program or service achieves the goals and objectives that are of greatest value to the community (GFOA, 2011). These calls for engagement of outside help where needed to design the process, develop successful communication plans, incorporate citizen involvement, and institute a process. Civil society organizations need to play their oversight role in ensuring transparency and accountability in the budget making process. Even though this has greatly been impeded by inadequate knowledge and capacity on social accountability, key measures need to be put in place lest we decentralize corruption in the new structures (Heraf, 2014).

In England, Lutz (2012) carried out a study to explore ways in which the local government authorities used their procurement function to foster sustainable development. The researcher reviewed existing literature using

exploratory approach and the findings were: Local government had adopted wide range initiatives that address all three aspects of sustainability: Economic, Environmental and Social. They concluded that local government had managed to perform because the three aspects of sustainability were rightly balanced and other local governments are using England as a benchmark. This is a clear indication that sustainable procurement will only play its roles: cost reduction, minimal impact to the environment, quality and service delivery, in organization if the economic, environmental and social aspects sustainable are rightly balanced and integrated in the procurement process.

Phusavat (2013) in the study of roles of public participation in developing and sustaining a networked government noted that for any public participation initiative to be successful the following as to be considered, the public must be aware of the impact of any activity they undertake, there must be continuous study and relevant information gathering and also the need to identify critical stakeholders. This suggests that most citizens are unlikely to participate in government projects as intended due to lack of information. It also worth noting that most county government based in rural areas are likely to be faced by ignorance and have high levels of illiteracy that calls for community sensitization and education.

According to Roos (2012), as a result of an increase in environmental, social, and economic problems in both developed and developing countries, Sustainable Public Procurement (SPP) is attracting a growing amount of attention. Government procurement accounts for about 15% of GDP in OECD countries and up to 25%-30% of GDP in developing countries, and governments are increasingly relying on it. It is evident that there is a growing need to involve members of public in key decision making mostly in regard to development projects by the county government and other government institutions, but the biggest question is to what extend and who should be involved so that the main objective is achieved without propelling personal interest at the same time ensuring its timeliness at minimal cost. Hence the following hypothesis was developed; *H₀₁: Procurement planning as a public participation strategy does not significantly influence sustainable procurement in devolved system of governments in Kenya.*

3.0 Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study target population was 1146 (Public Participation Coordinators, Project Coordinators, Procurement officers and Project management committee members) comprising of individuals who extensively participate in community-based infrastructure development projects. A sample size of 297 respondents was obtained using Slovin's formulae while stratified sampling method was used to obtain the study sample (Ali, 2014) from the three counties of Makueni, Machakos and Kitui. Primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire through drop and pick method within a period of 30 days. The study instrument was administered to 10% (30 respondents) of the sample to ensure that it was relevant and effective. These respondents were obtained from Embu county and hence did not form part of the final study sample so as to control response biasness. The obtained Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.878 from the pilot study was found sufficient for the study instrument. Data was analyzed using both descriptive, inferential statistics and linear regression model and results presented in tables.

4.0 Results and Discussions

A total of 289 questionnaires were completed and returned representing a 97.3 percent response rate, which was appropriate for the study. On whether the County Governments informed members of the community on need for public participation in county infrastructure projects, majority (96.6%) of the respondents agreed that the community is well involved in community infrastructural projects through different ways including town halls, websites, seminars and notice boards. When respondents were asked to indicate the level of awareness of the

existence of procurement opportunities within their county, 76% of the respondents indicated that the community was aware of procurement opportunities with only 24% indicating a contrary opinion. This shows that majority of the communities' members are aware of the procurement opportunities hence have an opportunity to participate in this process. These results indicate that majority of the citizens are aware of their county government procurement activities due to existence of different public participation strategies. This is the case since citizens are the direct beneficiaries of procurement output and to provide better services for citizens, social accountability is instrumental in ensuring the effectiveness of the procurement process and strengthening both national and county government. These findings are in line with Criado et al. (2013) who assert that nowadays we see an increasing number of governments on both the national and regional levels collaborating with externals, such as citizens, to stimulate social development by utilizing external knowledge. However, a necessary condition for collaborative value creation is citizen involvement (Voorberg et al., 2015), meaning it depends on citizens' willingness to interact with governmental institutions and provide input on the given task (Bekkers et al., 2013). Thus, the success of an open government approach is therefore influenced by the degree of public participation.

The study also sought to establish whether the county governments embraced public participation through the procurement planning process (project identification forums, budgeting exercise, procurement requirements) for sustainable procurement management. The respondents were asked to rate the statements concerning Procurement Planning. The four items evaluating Procurement Planning were rated on a five-point Likert type scale ranging from 1 representing "Not at all" to 5 designating " very large extent ". Table 1 indicates that the item mean scale for Procurement Planning ranged from 3.11 to 3.73. This implied that the respondents believed that involvement of community in Project Procurement planning was moderately practiced. The standard deviations of the Procurement Planning process items ranged from 1.259 to 1.344. The low standard deviations implied that the Procurement Planning item responses dispersed narrowly about the mean, implying low variations in the responses given by the respondents. The overall mean composite score for the Procurement Planning process scale was (Mean=3.34, SD=1.30, n=290) which denoted a moderate level of extent of involvement of community in Project Procurement planning process by the study respondents.

The study results indicate that the public is involved in project identification, choice of procurement method, project scheduling as well as project materials requirement. This is an indicator that the community is involved in the procurement planning process. These findings are supported by Cooper (2005) that Public participation is the process of engagement in governance, in which 'people participate together for deliberation and collective action within an array of interests, institutions and networks, developing civic identity, and involving people in governance processes. This is further supported by the fact that the devolved system of government, the County Government Act (Government of Kenya, 2012a), the Public Finance Management Act (GoK, 2012), and the Urban Areas and Cities Act (GoK, 2011) have called for public participation in drafting new legislation, determining budget priorities, ensuring that public-sector performance and expenditures are reviewed and submitting grievances.

In addition, County governments have been tasked with ensuring that the public receives information for public participation, setting in place structures and mechanisms and guidelines for public participation, and also providing an annual report on citizen participation to the County Assemblies. Public participation in Kenya's devolved system of government has had its fair share of challenges, such as limited support from the political class and low levels of civic education (Kenya School of Government, 2015). However, there has been a success story in Makueni County, whose public participation model has been lauded by the World Bank (2016). In its model, the County has been able to have the citizens identify their development priorities at the grassroots level, with the citizens becoming involved in the prioritization, planning and setting of final expenditures for the identified projects. Users are the start and end points of the procurement process. They are directly involved in a

number of activities and decisions such as adequate definition of the user's requirements/needs relating to materials to be purchased for example; estimated requirements/quantities, specifications, identifying minimum and desirable elements and ensuring that there is adequate in consultation with users and their representative bodies (Scottish Police Authority, 2008). Furthermore, Procurement teams also have to be able to listen to the stakeholders whom they are engaging with, and then be ready to sell back ideas as a result of those conversations (Dressler, 2015). Korten (1990) asserts that authentic community participation enhances the sustainability of the community development projects and this can only be achieved through a people centered development.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for Procurement Planning

Procurement Planning	Mean	Std. Deviation
	The community is involved in project identification	3.73
The community is involved in determining project procurement method	3.11	1.31
The county government involves the community in determining the project time schedule (time to start and end project)	3.31	1.26
The County Government involves community in determining the requirements of projects	3.20	1.34
Composite score	3.34	1.30

Diagnostic tests for the linear, nonlinear, and combined relationship between Procurement planning and Sustainable procurement was carried out. The test for linearity has a significance F value smaller than 0.05 ($F=535.787$, $P<0.05$), indicating that there is a linear relationship between Procurement planning and Sustainable procurement. The test for deviation from linearity (nonlinear) has insignificance F value, ($F=1.173$, $P=0.198$) which means that there is no nonlinear relationship in addition to the linear component as indicated in table 2.

Table 2: Test for linearity for the relationship between Procurement planning and Sustainable procurement

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Sustainable procurement management * Procurement planning	Between Groups	(Combined)	30.637	201	0.152	3.833	0.000
		Linearity	21.308	1	21.308	535.787	0.000
		Deviation from Linearity	9.329	200	0.047	1.173	0.198
	Within Groups		3.500	88	0.040		
Total			34.137	289			

Linear regression was used to test the relationship between Procurement Planning and sustainable procurement. Path coefficients were used to determine the direction and strength while t-statistic provided information on the significance of the relationships. The R^2 for the regression model between Procurement Planning and sustainable procurement was 0.434 meaning that Procurement Planning explained 43.4 % variation in the sustainable procurement while the remaining variation is explained by the error term as shown on table 3

Table 3: Model Summary for Procurement Planning on Sustainable Procurement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.659 ^a	.434	.432	.31085

a. Predictors: (Constant), Procurement planning

The regression model was a good fit as indicated by a significant F-statistic ($F=220.516$, $p<0.05$).

Table 4: ANOVA for Procurement Planning on sustainable procurement

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	21.308	1	21.308	220.516	.000 ^b
	Residual	27.829	288	.097		
	Total	49.137	289			

a. Dependent Variable: Sustainable procurement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Procurement planning

The regression model obtained from the output was;

Sustainable procurement = $1.589 + 0.484$ Procurement planning + error as shown on table 5. The standardized regression coefficient for Procurement planning was 0.659. This indicates that a unit increase in the Procurement planning would result in 65.9% increase in the sustainable procurement. The t-statistic for the regression coefficient for Procurement planning was significant at 5% level of significance ($T=14.850$, $p<0.05$) implying rejection of null hypothesis. On the basis of these statistics, the study concludes that there is significant positive relationship between Procurement planning and sustainable procurement. Stakeholders are affected in both positive and negative ways due to the different stages and nature of the procurement process from identification of the needs to contract closure (Olander, 2007). The procedure should be exposed to user inspection, depending on the procurement technique used and any privacy agreement stemming from that particular procurement technique employed (Noelia, 2016) user involvement in purchasing may create and maintain relationships suppliers enhancing partnership between the organization and its suppliers (Bateman, 2015). User involvement in procurement complies primarily with contract or viable law with respect to the establishment of agreements, but their methods of procurement are ruled by business rules. In order for the purchasing department to deliver products and services that meet the user needs, there is need to involve the users themselves when making decisions relating to purchasing (Perreau, 2015). They are directly involved in a number of activities and decisions such as adequate definition of the user's requirements/needs relating to materials to be purchased for example; estimated requirements/quantities, specifications, identifying minimum and desirable elements and ensuring that there is adequate in consultation with users and their representative bodies (Scottish Police Authority, 2008). A number of scholars (Kabonga, 2016; Kessler & Tanburn, 2014; Metzger & Guenther, 2015; World Bank, 2010) have argued that development should be assessed on four significant fronts—that is effectiveness, efficiency, impact, and sustainability. Ahmed (2018) Citizens are the stakeholders with the right to know how their money is being spent in public procurement activities.

Table 5: Coefficients for Procurement Planning on sustainable procurement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.589	.099		16.109	.000
	Procurement planning	.484	.033	.659	14.850	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Sustainable procurement

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

The study found that there exists a relationship between procurement planning and sustainable procurement in devolved systems of Government in Kenya. From the forgoing, it can be concluded that an improvement in procurement planning leads to a positive improvement in sustainable procurement management in devolved systems of Government in Kenya. In conclusion, the County governments need to adopt effective procurement

planning techniques so as to reap the benefits of public participation in procurement process for sustainable procurement management. This is so since procurement planning leads to a positive improvement in sustainable procurement management in devolved systems of Government in Kenya. The study recommends that further research be done to address the limitations of this study. This study considered only the south eastern development block; Kitui, Machakos and Makueni counties future researchers could consider carrying out a similar study in a different block or counties to assess any variation in responses. It would be interesting to explore how the results obtained when the methods applied in this study are applied in other contexts for example in other countries at higher or lower stages of development. It would be worthwhile establishing the extent to which the findings of this study are generalizable to other industries, sectors or settings.

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